

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GHOSE****FIRST NAME: SOUMITA****PROGRAM CODE : PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: Microsoft 365 2024 on MacOS

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the primary purpose of using a period?

To end a declarative statement.¹

To separate items in a list.

To indicate a pause.

To emphasize a word.

2. Where should a table be situated in a research manuscript?

Immediately after the section in which it is mentioned for the first time.²

At the end of the paper.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 316.

² Turabian, 382.

- In the appendix section of the paper.
 - At the beginning of the chapter, which contains the table.
3. How do you span a table into multiple pages?
- Repeat the stub column and all column heads on all pages.**³
 - Omit the title of the table on subsequent pages.
 - Use a small font to fit the table on one page.
 - Put the table in the annexure.
4. What is the purpose of the epigraph?
- To establish a theme for the paper.**⁴
 - To function as a reference list.
 - To provide a summary of the paper.
 - To acknowledge the contributors to the research.
5. What should a working introduction section of research focus on?
- Summary of the key points and sources.**⁵
 - Detailed analysis of sources.
 - Detailed methodology discussion.
 - Comprehensive literature review.

³ Turabian, 428.

⁴ Turabian, 374.

⁵ Turabian, 70.

6. How does storyboard help in research papers?
- To outline the structure of the research.**⁶
 - To present the final draft.
 - To list all relevant sources.
 - To summarize the pre-existing literature on the topic.
7. What kind of problems do applied research projects address?
- Conceptual problems.**⁷
 - Procedural problems.
 - Theoretical problems.
 - Hypothetical problems.
8. Which chapter in the dissertation is reviewed by the supervisory committee for appropriateness of the research questions and methods?
- Dissertation prospectus.**⁸
 - Dissertation manuscript.
 - Dissertation concept paper.
 - Dissertation defense.
9. What does procedural schema do in a dissertation?

⁶ Turabian, 32.

⁷ Turabian, 29.

⁸ James P. Sampson, *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee, Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 10.

Understanding the relationship among dissertation sections.⁹

- Provides a framework for literature review.
- Identifies the research variables.
- Helps in developing the research hypothesis.

10. What is one of the critical characteristics of a working hypothesis?

It may change as the research progresses.¹⁰

- It may mislead the researcher.
- It may restrict the research exploration.
- It needs to be final.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Sampson, James P. *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee, Florida: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

⁹ Sampson, 23.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition*, 31.

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